

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel tetrahydroquinoline and tetrahydroisoquinoline analogues

Swastika Ganguly* and S. Murugesan

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi-835 215, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : pompi123@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : A series of tetrahydroquinoline and tetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives were synthesized and their structures were confirmed by spectral (FT-IR, NMR and Mass) data analysis. These analogs were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇Rv strain) and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*.

Keywords : Tetrahydroquinoline, tetrahydroisoquinoline, antibacterial, antimycobacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

Compounds with quinoline and isoquinoline nucleus exhibit potent antiviral¹⁻⁴, anti-tubercular⁵⁻⁹, antibacterial¹⁰, antifungal^{11,12}, antimalarial¹³⁻¹⁵ and anticancer¹⁶ activities since ancient days. In view of the above reports, we wish to report the synthesis, characterization

and evaluation of some novel *N*-substituted 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline and 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives (Schemes 1, 2 and 3) and their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against standard Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria as well as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and fungi.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of compounds 1a-c and 2a-c.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of compounds 1d and 2d.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of compounds 1e-f and 2e-f.

Results and discussion

The title compounds were synthesized as presented in Schemes 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The chloroanilides were prepared by the reported method¹⁷. The compounds 1a-c and 2a-c were prepared by condensing 1,2,3,4-

tetrahydroquinoline/1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline with appropriate chloroanilides. The compounds 1d and 2d were synthesized by treating phthalimide with formaldehyde and 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline/1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline. Compounds 1e and 2e were synthesized by

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of compounds 1b-e and 2b-f

Compd	R	Y	Ar	Molecular formula	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	IR (cm ⁻¹)	MS (m/z)	¹ H NMR (δ)
1b	CH ₃	CO NH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	78-84	53	3261 (NH), 2929 (CH), 1666 (C=O), 1369 (CN)	280 (M+)	1.8 (3H, d, CH-CH ₃), 2.0 (2H, m, H-2), 2.9 (2H, t, H-3), 3.5 (2H, t, H-1), 4.5 (1H, q, CH-CH ₃), 7.1-7.7 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.2 (1H, s, NH)
1c	H	CH ₂ -CO NH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	82-90	83	3273 (NH), 1664 (C=O), 1330 (CN)	281 (M+)	1.9 (2H, m, H-2), 2.6 (2H, t, N-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CONH), 2.7 (2H, t, H-3), 3 (2H, t, H-1), 3.7 (2H, t, N-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CONH), 6.5-7.6 (9H, m, Ar-H)
2b	CH ₃	C=O NH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	165-170	82	3277 (NH), 2835 (CH), 1691 (C=O), 1332 (CN)	281 (M+)	1.42 (3H, d, CH-CH ₃), 2.85 (2H, t, H-3), 2.95 (2H, t, H-2), 3.41 (1H, q, CH-CH ₃), 7.0-7.6 (9H, m, Ar-H)
2c	H	CH ₂ -C=O NH	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	92-100	88	3298 (NH), 1662 (C=O), 1323 (CN)	281 (M+)	2.2 (2H, s, H-1), 2.3 (2H, t, CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CONH), 2.7 (2H, t, CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CONH), 2.9 (2H, t, H-3), 3.5 (2H, t, H-2), 6.9-7.6 (9H, m, Ar-H)
2d	H	N-(C=O) ₂	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	176-180	74	2900 (CH), 1701 (C=O), 1313 (CN)	293 (M+)	2.29 (2H, t, H-3), 2.98 (2H, t, H-2), 3.8 (2H, s, H-1), 4.8 (2H, s, N-CH ₂ -N), 7.0-7.1 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, dd, H-2',3'), 7.9 (2H, dd, H-1',4')
2e	H	C=O	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNO	78-84	79	2897 (CH), 1693 (C=O), 1398 (CN), 650 (C-Cl)	286 (M+)	0.9 (2H, t, H-3), 1.3 (2H, t, H 2), 3.5 (2H, s, N-CH ₂ -CO), 4.1 (2H, s, H-1), 7.6 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.1 (2H, d, H-1',4'), 8.3 (2H, d, H-2',3')
2f	H	CH-OH	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ClNO	70-74	57	3600 (CH-OH), 2900 (CH), 1352 (CN), 819 (C-Cl)	289 (M+)	2.0 (1H, s, -OH), 2.7 (2H, d, -N-CH ₂ -CH(OH)), 3.5 (2H, s, H-1), 5.1 (1H, t, -N-CH ₂ -CH(OH)), 6.8-7.1 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.65 (2H, d, Ar-H), 8.25 (2H, d, Ar-H)

Note

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of compounds **1a-f** and **2a-f**

Compd.	MIC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)					
	<i>S. aureus</i> NCIM 2901	<i>B. subtilis</i> MTCC 441	<i>S. faecalis</i> NCIM 5024	<i>E. coli</i> NCIM 2810	<i>Ps. aeruginosa</i> NCIM 2036	<i>S. typhi</i> NCIM 2501
1a	100	100	> 100	100	100	100
1b	50	50	25	50	50	50
1c	50	25	25	25	25	25
1d	50	25	50	50	25	50
1e	50	50	25	50	50	50
1f	50	25	25	25	25	50
2a	50	25	50	25	25	50
2b	50	25	50	50	50	50
2c	12.5	12.5	25	25	12.5	25
2d	50	25	50	50	25	50
2e	25	25	50	25	12.5	50
2f	25	12.5	25	25	12.5	50
Ciprofloxacin	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78

reacting *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide with 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline/1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline¹⁸. The compounds **1f** and **2f** were synthesized by reducing the corresponding 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3,4-dihydroquinolin-1(2*H*)-yl)ethanone (**1e**)/1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3,4-dihydroisoquinolin-2(1*H*)-yl)ethanone (**2e**) by sodium borohydride¹⁹. The structures of the synthesized compounds (Table 1) were confirmed by FT-IR, ¹H NMR and MS spectral data. The purity of the compounds was ascertained by elemental analysis. In the FT-IR spectra, characteristic absorption bands at 3400–3200, 1700–1600 and 3600 cm^{-1} confirm the presence of N–H, C=O and –OH functional group in the synthesized compounds respectively. In the ¹H NMR spectra, the chemical shift values in terms of ppm for methylene, aromatic and –NH protons were seen at 2.0–3.9, 6.5–7.6 and 8.2–9.0 ppm respectively and were according to the expected values. The MS of the compounds were recorded using Fast Atom Bombardment technique. In the Mass spectra, molecular ion peaks were seen for the title compounds. The base peak forms by the rupture of side chain methylene group from 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline and 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline nucleus. Finally, the elemental analysis results were also consistent with the postulated structures.

The synthesized compounds were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against standard organisms [Gram-positive bacteria : *Staphylococcus aureus* NCIM

2901, *Bacillus subtilis* MTCC 441, *Streptococcus faecalis* NCIM 5024; Gram-negative bacteria : *Escherichia coli* NCIM 2810, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* NCIM 2036, *Salmonella typhi* NCIM 2501] by two fold serial broth dilution method^{18–21}, antimycobacterial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv (ATCC 27294) in BACTEC 12B medium by Microplate Alamar Blue Assay (MABA)^{24,25}, and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* MTCC 227 and *Aspergillus niger* MTCC 282 by two fold serial broth dilution method^{18–23}. The results are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 3. Antimycobacterial activity of compounds **1a-f** and **2a-f**

Compd.	IC ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	IC ₉₀ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
1a	> 100	> 100
1b	55.05	80.90
1c	> 100	> 100
1d	> 100	> 100
1e	37.12	> 100
1f	> 100	> 100
2a	56.77	75.89
2b	49.87	51.70
2c	30.14	43.84
2d	> 100	> 100
2e	24.81	26.99
2f	25.07	70.50
Amikacin	0.07	0.07

Table 4. Antifungal activity of compounds 1a-f and 2a-f

Compd.	MIC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1a	25	25
1b	50	50
1c	25	25
1d	50	50
1e	50	50
1f	50	50
2a	25	25
2b	50	50
2c	25	12.5
2d	50	25
2e	50	25
2f	25	12.5
Fluconazole	12.5	12.5

Compound 2c exhibited moderate activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Compound 2e showed moderate activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* while compound 2f showed moderate activity against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. All other compounds exhibited weak activity against all the strains when compared to the standard drug ciprofloxacin.

Compounds 2e and 2f showed some inhibitory activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* but were much less active than the standard drug amikacin. All other compounds were found to exhibit weak activity.

All the compounds exhibited moderate activity against *C. albicans* while compounds 2c and 2f showed significant inhibitory activity comparable to that of standard drug fluconazole against *A. niger*. All other compounds exhibited moderate activity against *A. niger*.

Experimental

All the m.p.s were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR series 1020 spectrometer (Japan). ^1H NMR was recorded using Jeol D-300 MHz Bruker FT-NMR spectrometer using CDCl_3 as solvent (Germany). Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol D-300 spectrometer using Fast Atom Bombardment (FAB positive). Elemental analysis was performed on a Vario Elementor C, H, N, S-O analyzer. The elemental analysis results were within

$\pm 0.4\%$ of theoretical values. The reactions were monitored by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) carried out on activated silica gel coated plates and the solvent system used was chloroform : benzene : methanol (3 : 0.3 : 0.1). Yields, melting point and spectral data for the synthesized compounds 1, 2 and 3 are recorded in Table 1.

2-(3,4-Dihydroquinolin-1(2H)-yl)-N-phenylacetamide (1a) :

To a solution of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline (0.012 mol) in 16.7 ml of acetonitrile, the appropriate chloroanilide (0.012 mol) and triethylamine (0.024 mol) were added drop wise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into crushed ice and was treated with solid potassium carbonate to yield precipitate which was filtered, washed with water (3×100 ml) and finally with *n*-hexane (3×20 ml). The solid residue obtained was dried and recrystallized from ethanol to yield crystals of 1a (84%), m.p. 94–98 °C (Found : C, 76.48; H, 6.54; N, 10.35. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 76.66; H, 6.81; N, 10.52%). IR (cm^{-1}) 3269 (NH stretching), 1666 (C=O stretching), 1369 (CN stretching). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) (δ ppm) 2.1 (2H, m, N-H-2), 2.85 (2H, t, H-3), 3.35 (2H, t, H-1), 3.90 (2H, s, N- CH_2 -CO), 6.50–7.64 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.40 (1H, s, NH). Mass (m/z) 267 [$\text{M}^+ + 1$] (38), 265 (5), 146 (72), 134 (10), 132 (5). All other compounds 1b-c were prepared by similar procedure using appropriate chloroanilides.

2-(3,4-Dihydroisoquinolin-2(1H)-yl)-N-phenylacetamide (2a) :

To a solution of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (0.012 mol) in 16.7 ml of acetonitrile the appropriate chloroanilide (0.012 mol) and triethylamine (0.024 mol) were added drop wise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into crushed ice and was treated with solid potassium carbonate to yield precipitate which was filtered, washed with water (3×100 ml) and finally with *n*-hexane (3×20 ml). The solid residue obtained was dried and recrystallized from ethanol to yield crystals of 2a (82%), m.p. 42–44 °C (Found : C, 76.02; H, 6.80; N, 10.51. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires : C, 76.66; H, 6.81; N, 10.52%). IR (cm^{-1}) 3315 (NH stretching), 1660 (C=O stretching), 1340 (CN stretching). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) (δ ppm) 2.9 (2H, t, H-3), 3.0 (2H, t, H-2), 3.35 (2H, s, N- CH_2 -CO), 3.8 (2H, s,

H-1), 7.0–7.6 (9H, m, Ar-H), 9.1 (1H, s, NH). Mass (*m/z*) 267 [$M^+ + 1$] (100), 266 [M^+] (50), 265 (80), 264 (20), 146 (75), 134 (10), 132 (30), 120 (10). All other compounds **2b–c** were prepared in the same manner using appropriate chloranilides.

2-((3,4-Dihydroquinolin-1(2H)-yl)methyl)isoindoline-1,3-dione (1d) :

To a solution of phthalimide (0.02 mol) in 35 ml of ethanol (95%), 2 ml of formaldehyde (37%) was added. The mixture was refluxed until all the amide has been dissolved. Appropriate amount of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline was added to the hot ethanolic solution and the reflux was continued for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice bath at 0–5 °C. The resulting precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to yield **1d** (64%), m.p. 260–262 °C (Found : C, 73.65; H, 5.49; N, 9.29. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires : C, 73.95; H, 5.52; N, 9.58%). IR (cm^{-1}) 1732 (C=O stretching), 1307 (CN stretching). 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) (δ ppm) 1.8 (2H, m, H-2), 2.57 (2H, t, H-3), 3.8 (2H, t, N-H-1), 5.23 (2H, s, N- CH_2 -N), 6.6–7.3 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.6–7.7 (2H, dd, H-1',4'), 7.8–7.9 (2H, dd, H-2',3'). Mass (*m/z*) 292 [M^+] (30), 291 (70), 290 (30), 289 (50), 160 (80), 146 (100), 132 (30). The compound **2d** was prepared similarly using tetrahydroisoquinoline.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-(3,4-dihydroquinolin-1(2H)-yl)ethanone (1e) :

To a stirred solution of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline (0.03 mol) in 10 ml of dimethyl formamide, *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide (0.015 mol) was added in such a manner that the temperature did not rise above 5 °C. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 5 h at ice cold condition. The mixture was then poured into water and stirred. The precipitate was collected and then treated with benzene and filtered. The benzene soluble portion on removal of solvent yielded a solid mass, which was crystallized from alcohol yielded **1e** (72%), m.p. 70–80 °C (Found : C, 71.40; H, 5.70; N, 5.01. $C_{17}H_{16}ClNO$ requires : C, 71.45; H, 5.64; N, 4.90%). IR (cm^{-1}) 2918 (CH stretching), 1697 (C=O stretching), 1346 (CN stretching), 559 (C-Cl stretching). 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) (δ ppm) 2.0 (2H, m, H-2), 2.8 (2H, t, H-3), 3.4 (2H, t, H-1), 4.7 (2H, s, N- CH_2 -CO), 6.4–7.2 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.1 (2H, d, H-1',4'), 8.3 (2H, d, H-2',3'). Mass (*m/z*) 286 [M^+] (40),

251 (60), 146 (90). The compound **2e** was prepared similarly using tetrahydroisoquinoline.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-(3,4-dihydroquinolin-1(2H)-yl)ethanol (1f) :

An equimolar mixture of **1e** (0.03 mol) and sodium borohydride (0.03 mol) in 300 ml of methanol was refluxed for 8 h. After solvent evaporation, 20 ml of water was added to the residue. The mixture was neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid and then refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solution was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide. The precipitate obtained was collected, dried and recrystallized from acetone yielded crystals of **1f** (58%), m.p. 96–100 °C (Found : C, 70.88; H, 6.38; N, 4.92. $C_{17}H_{18}ClNO$ requires : C, 70.95; H, 6.30; N, 4.87%). IR (cm^{-1}) 3638 (CH-OH stretching), 2943 (CH stretching), 1346 (CN stretching), 752 (C-Cl stretching). 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) (δ ppm) 1.7 (1H, s, -OH), 2.0 (2H, m, H-2), 2.6 (2H, t, H-3), 3.0 (2H, t, H-1), 3.6 (2H, d, N- CH_2 -CH(OH)), 4.8 (1H, t, - CH_2 -CH(OH)), 7.7–7.8 (8H, m, Ar-H). Mass (*m/z*) 288 [M^+] (60), 146 (90), 139 (40), 132 (60). The compound **2f** was prepared similarly using **2e**.

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